

[Name of the Writer]

[Subject]

[Date]

Wordsworth: Tintern Abbey

William Wordsworth is known for the poems he composed during the Romantic Era. One of the most famous poems presented by him is "Lines Composed A Few Miles from Tintern Abbey." In this poem, he explores his memory; he also portrayed his current viewing of Tintern Abbey. He looks back on the past five years that have gone by since his first visit to Tintern Abbey remembering how much the memory of this scene meant to him and their impacts on his life. He relied on these memories to keep him sane from "the din of towns and cities". They then led him to a blessed and spiritual meditative state. Wordsworth's Romantic views of nature are even more evident in this poem because he presents his personal responses to show his impressions, the memory of what he felt before, and the thought of how he will look back on this moment in the future. The poem serves as a manifesto for Romantic poetry by using real language and scenes of everyday life to create a state of deep sensation. In the entire poem, he kept on describing the things around him and how they are making him feel good. He explains the voice of rolling water around him, and he develops the tone of soothing atmosphere and Wordsworth makes himself part of that nature with no hesitation (Eldridge 10).

In this poem William Wordsworth, desire to portray what he saw as oneness of the human psyche through the universal mind of cosmos. He made a pantheistic attempt in order to explain the unfurl essence of nature's sublime mystery, which has evades the understanding. He displayed himself as the young writer, who firmly rooted through the revolutionary traditions.

This has made him confused that which way to proceed morally or socially and later, he defines himself as the personal socio-political vision. Regarding the naturalistic depiction in "Tintern Abbey" it showed the nature's interconnection with humanity and universe. This lyrical ballad reveals the Samuel Coleridge and John Thelwall implicit influence on the Wordsworth progression as both the writer and naturalist poet (Brennan 13)

In the poem, Wordsworth began describing the surroundings, he explain that how vivid and faint Tintern Abey is displayed in his mind. This makes him to recall the unremembered pleasure, which depict readers that there are few things, which he did not remember as brilliantly as he remembers other things naturally and respectfully. However, he has faced difficult time in remembering every detail; he has gone through an effortless experience in order to feel his soul come to life. The poem allows him to be the living soul and to see the life of things. Wordsworth absorbs all, which is around him and he reflected on his memories.

Wordsworth begins by describing the "beauteous forms" or memories of this place. The poet is shifting his attention from the place he is present to recapitulate his memories of it and the effects these memories have on his emotions. In a sense he is having a flashback in which he is reliving the emotions he felt during the past five years through witnessing nature. Man and nature are essentially meant to interact and nature can mirror the mind of man. He continues to describe that these memories are forever present to him such as a "landscape is to a bind man's eye". This comparison gives a reality to the importance of how the vivid imagines of nature drive his life and essentially they are forever a part of him (Eldridge 10).

He felt somehow the memories were present in his "blood" and "felt in his heart". They cannot be separated from the body such as the blood is essential for the body thrive. Though, this Wordsworth is showing the effects of nature over time on the human body and soul.

The theme of the poem is beneficial influence of nature. Throughout the poem, the poet explains that nature is the core factor, which provides the ultimate positive influence on the human mind. Through the manifestation of natural world, from the mountains to the simplest flower elevate the passionate emotions and thoughts in the people who feel close to such manifestations. Throughout the poem, he emphasized on the importance of nature on the individuals spiritual and intellectual development.

The naturalism theory presented in that era, explains that good relationship with the nature helps individual to connect themselves with both to social worlds and spiritual. In the Prelude, Wordsworth, explains that the love of nature could lead towards the love of humankind. Wordsworth in this lyrical ballad has praised the power of human mind. He explained that by using imagination and memory, people could overcome with their pain and difficulty. As speaker in the poem portrayed his loneliness from the memories of nature, he explained that leech is gatherer in the resolution and independence; he faced the poverty cheerfully through the exertion of his own will (Gravil 39)

He believed that the transformative powers regarding mind are present in all, it is available regardless of the individual background and class. He explained his view as democratic, which emphasizes on the uniqueness and individuality.

Throughout his poem, he has portrayed the strong support to the religious, artistic and political rights of an individual, which includes the power of mind. Nature has always inspired Wordsworth poetically. It provides him with the landscape of seclusion, which implies the deepening of the mood regarding seclusion in the mind of Wordsworth. Wordsworth uses his memories of nature to calm himself and to restore his tranquility. This calming effect also happens when he is physically looking at nature. Once again the distractions of the eyes are referenced. It is only when our eyes are quiet and relaxed that we can see life (Gravil 39). In

nature, when eyes are shut or focused, sounds are amplified, movement is felt. Sometimes eyes seem to distract, hiding the life within nature, which to Wordsworth is more important than beauty.

He now understands the deeper meaning of nature; it is something beyond the surface. He maintains his love for it, but now realizes that the eyes “half create” and change what something truly is. As Wordsworth is given time to reflect on what he sees, he understands that the beauty of nature is not aesthetic, rather it is found in its ability to clear the mind of problems. It is important to allow the brain to show the answers and to show love. He will forever remain a worshiper of nature because of the memories it inspires, what it shows him and what nature reminds him of. All of these things go beyond his eyes. Nature goes deeper. It moves through his veins into his heart, restores tranquility and reminds him of the important parts of life (Peters 74).

All of these aspects contribute to Wordsworth's identity. He has changed over the five years he has been gone from Tintern Abbey and has learned to see with more than his eyes. His ability to see beyond the surface of nature shows the importance of what is under his surface. Identity is not about the external. This is why discovering someone's true identity takes more than a simple glance. Identity must be deciphered in one's mind (Miall 4)

Nature allows him to first be comforted in times of need, creating a tranquil being that then can reflect on all aspect of life. This “tranquility” leads him to a trance like state in which spiritually everything can be seen more vividly. The idea of nature affecting someone to this degree is mind blowing. Wordsworth believes the memories of nature enable people to exceed the state of normal human life and move towards the direction of being divine. For Wordsworth nature itself does not move people, it is the memories of nature that creates this spiritual trace like state of being divine.

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